
THE CONCEPT OF "EDUCATING YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM" AND ITS ROLE IN YOUTH EDUCATION

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Annotation.

the article is informed on the basis of the basic principles and priorities of the state policy on youth implemented in the country, in the current complex era of globalization, in a situation where information and communication technologies are rapidly developing, current tasks related to the education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism and ways to solve them, determines the role and importance

Keywords.

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Patriotism is a concept that expresses the love and loyalty of people to their native land, to their own oshyon. Patriotism is one of the universal feeling, spiritual values, common to all people, people, Nations, polished for centuries. Historically, patriotism is also a set of historiography, which has been improved in the process of Social Development, the struggle of people for the inviolability and independence of the territory in which they live, related to the fate of their homeland. It is manifested in pride in the past and present of the motherland, in the protection of its interests. It was not for nothing that the love of the motherland is from faith. Activities to educate the growing young generation in the spirit of spiritual and moral and military patriotism, in which the formation of a sense of

duty to protect the sovereignty and independence of the country are being carried out in our country in rapid pictures. On the initiative of our president, on the basis of Resolution No. 140 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 23, 2018, the concept of "educating young people in the spirit of patriotism" was developed, consisting of 7 chapters. In this concept, the issue of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism is considered as an integral and integral part of the holistic education and education system for the upbringing of a physically and spiritually healthy generation, and in 2017-2021, special attention was paid to the issue of advanced experiences in the national and world based on the requirements. The need to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism, to prepare them physically and spiritually for the defense of the Motherland is one of the urgent tasks of the present day. Training of students in general educational institutions, secondary special and secondary vocational educational institutions, including students and young people studying in higher education institutions in the spirit of military patriotism, is now carried out through all systems of educational work. In fact, genuine loyalty to the motherland also requires being able to protect it. Education of students in the spirit of military patriotism is the main place of all kinds of functioning educational institutions. In accordance with the concept, educational work in the spirit of military-patriotism is carried out mainly in four stages:

The first stage (3-7 years old) is considered the stage in which initial visions of the surrounding world, Homeland appear, which involves teaching children various poems, songs and songs in family and preschool institutions, showing cartoons and various games, realizing the world through drawing pictures, forming love for the motherland in them based on acquaintance with state symbols (flag, coat of arms, anthem).

- telling fairy tales and stories in order to form initial visions in the military-patriotic direction;

- memorizing poems and songs on topics related to love for the motherland, the sacred duty of the protection of the motherland;

- organize various competitions and competitions to create drawings and strengthen the physical capacity of children to expand their imagination, thereby encouraging them spiritually;

- show cartoons on the theme of military-patriotism and conduct various games;

- organize excursions to cultural and recreational parks related to military museums and the theme of military-patriotism;

At the second stage (children aged 7-16 years), students are encouraged to do noble deeds, such as strengthening love and loyalty to the motherland, increasing their enthusiasm for military service and the fulfillment of the duty of childhood before the motherland with high responsibility, further strengthening positive thoughts towards our gunmen, forming young people as a physically healthy, strong and strong spiritual

- articles about heroes of our time, reading fiction;

- military-patriotic orientation in general secondary educational institutions

Organization of cultural events, themed evenings and song competitions, showing plaques from performances;

- Organization of a competition of essays on the topics "I will save my homeland as a blind eye", "fate of the land – my destiny " with the participation of reader youth;

- Organization of sports competitions and events on such topics as "followers of Temurbek", "children of Uzbekistan will be immersed" at health camps;

- presentation of artistic and documentary films, cartoons and their discussion on the topic of military-patriotism;

-introduction of information about the life and work of our great commanders into textbooks and educational and methodological manuals, telling stories based on vivid examples of their courage, dedication and heroism;

- Organization of excursions to special groups and military units of schools, higher military educational institutions, vocational colleges and academic lyceums;

-special importance is attached to the step-by-step Organization of military-sports games" successors of Temurbek " with the participation of upper-class students of general secondary education schools

The third stage (adolescents aged 16-18 years) is aimed at ensuring spiritual and physical readiness in young people to serve the motherland and worthy for its protection.

- to give detailed information about the need for physically strong and spiritually mature youth for our national army, the importance of military service, reforms in the Armed Forces;

The fourth stage (18-30 years old) provides for the physical and spiritual ability of young people, leadership skills and intellectual potential, general and

professional competence, to regularly work on themselves, encourage them to live a healthy life and achieve this.

This concept serves as a methodological basis for improving the effectiveness of military-patriotic education among young people, increasing knowledge and skills aimed at improving them with high spiritual and moral qualities, civil positivity, love of the motherland and preserving it as a teardrop. Of great importance in the education of student – youth military patriotism is the widespread use of the rules of pedagogy and psychology.

Military education is a complex socio-pedagogical process, in which it is mainly necessary to understand the following: to build student – youth with knowledge, skills and qualifications; to educate in them the necessary personal qualities for the armed defender of his homeland; to develop as a perfect person, to develop skills of a creative approach to solving various tasks that have arisen, and to It allows citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan to exalt their sense of patriotism, increase their responsibility to serve the motherland with dedication and loyalty, fill the ranks of the National Army with young people with modern knowledge and professional qualifications, strong will, active civil position.

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